

Visualization Use During Process Mining Analysis

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– Appendix –

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Road Traffic Fine Management Process

Figure 1. Simplified indication of the process flow captured in the Road Traffic Fine Management event log.

Participant Details

The table contains the overview of the 33 analysts (**ID**) who participated in our study. It highlights the **sector** to which the analysts' affiliation/company belongs, their job **role** at the time of the data collection, their self-rated **expertise** in process mining (ranked on a Likert-scale with values "novice", "basic", "average", "good", "advanced"), and the number of conducted projects before the study (**#Projects**). Additionally, we highlight the **tools used** during the study and the duration of their analyses (**Duration**).

ID	Sector	Role	Expertise	#Projects	Tool(s) Used	Duration
p1	Enterprise Software	Product Manager	Good	1	Celonis	0:32:58
p2	Academia	PhD Student	Average	1	Disco, Celonis	0:38:50
p3	National Laboratory	Senior R&D Staff	Good	2-5	Disco	0:33:59
p4	Consulting	Senior R&D Staff	Average	1	Disco, ProM	0:44:41
p5	Consumer Goods	Process Analyst	Average	2-5	Celonis	0:45:19
p6	Freelance	Process Mining Consultant	Good	2-5	Disco, ProM	1:27:14
p7	Academia	Professor	Advanced	6-10	Disco	0:42:16
p8	Academia	Assistant Professor	Advanced	2-5	Celonis, ProM	0:37:57
p9	Enterprise Software	Process Mining Consultant	Good	>20	Celonis	0:33:16
p10	Academia	Senior Researcher	Novice	None	Disco	0:34:59
p11	Freelance	Business Analyst	Advanced	6-10	Disco	0:43:38
p12	Academia	Assistant Professor	Advanced	2-5	ProM	0:40:06
p13	Enterprise Software	Partner Relationships Manager	Basic	1	Celonis	0:35:12
p14	Enterprise Software	Product Manager / Engineer	Good	10-20	Celonis	0:37:59
p15	Academia	Assistant Professor	Good	2-5	ProM, Disco	0:45:39
p16	Academia	PhD Student	Average	2-5	Disco	0:34:39
p17	Enterprise Software	Process Mining Consultant	Good	10-20	Celonis	0:36:50
p18	Academia	Assistant Professor	Advanced	6-10	Disco, ProM	0:36:46
p19	Enterprise Software	Partner Relationships Manager	Basic	1	Celonis	0:29:21
p20	Academia	Graduate Student	Average	None	Disco, ProM, Pm4Py	0:49:28
p21	Academia	Graduate Student	Basic	1	Disco	0:20:41
p22	Enterprise Software	Process Mining Consultant	Average	2-5	Celonis	0:41:01
p23	Enterprise Software	Analytics Product Manager	Good	2-5	Celonis	0:34:39
p24	Packaging	Digital Project Manager	Good	2-5	Disco	0:33:20
p25	Academia	Professor	Good	2-5	Disco	0:37:29
p26	Academia	PhD Student	Good	2-5	Disco, ProM	0:37:17
p27	Professor	Professor	Average	2-5	Disco	0:31:14
p28	Academia	PhD Student	Average	2-5	Disco, ProM	0:35:21
p29	Constructions	Operational Excellence Lead	Advanced	6-10	Celonis	0:36:26
p30	Insurance	Process Analyst	Good	2-5	Disco	0:33:40
p31	Insurance	Operational Excellence Lead	Advanced	>20	Disco	0:36:11
p32	Academia	Professor	Good	6-10	Celonis, Disco	0:39:39
p33	Academia	Senior Researcher	Advanced	10-20	ProM	0:43:28

Visualization Perspective – Coding Scheme

Below, we provide details about the visualization types that were used during our observational study. We add screenshots of each visualization type from the different tools to indicate their visual interfaces.

Visualization Type					
L1	L2	L3	Reference	Data Type	Tools
Net- work- based	Process Map	Process Explorer	[1]	Network Data	Celonis, Disco, ProM
		Variant Explorer		Network Data	Celonis
	-	Petri net	[2]	Network Data	ProM
		IvM Model	[3]	Network Data	ProM
		Causal Net	[4]	Network Data	ProM
		Social Network	[5]	Network Data	ProM
		BPMN	[6]	Network Data	Celonis
Time- line- based	-	Trace Sequence		Temporal data	Disco, ProM
		Variant Sequence		1-dimensional data	ProM
Chart- based	-	Dotted Chart	[7]	Multi-dimensional	ProM
		Line Graph		Temporal data	Celonis, Disco
		Bar Chart		2-dimensional data	Celonis, Disco
		Scatterplot		Multi-dimensional	Celonis

Process Map – Process Explorer

The Process Explorer displays a process model in a graph-like structure. Based on the implementation, the level of detail (how many relations and activities are displayed) can be selected. Additionally, annotations can be added to the nodes and edges of the graph. Those typically depict the case (trace) frequency (in how many traces of the event log the activity or relation was observed) or performance information, such as the mean or median throughput time for activities or the transition from one activity to another.

Figure 2. DFG in the “Process Explorer” in Celonis. The sliders on the right allow users to change the level of detail for the graph. Annotations can be changed by selecting the top left icon. Here also custom metrics can be defined.

Figure 3. DFG in Disco (called “Process Map”). In the window on the right, users can change the level of detail for the graph and select annotations based on pre-defined metrics.

Figure 4. Process Explorer in ProM.

Process Map – Variant Explorer

Like the Process Explorer the Variant Explorer displays a DFG. However, instead of setting the level of detail for activities and paths, users can select variants (sets of traces with the same sequence of activities).

Figure 5. DFG in the "Variant Explorer" in Celonis.

Petri net

The Petri net is a mathematical modeling language that is mainly used to describe distributed systems. However, it can be applied to processes to model them as a set of states and transitions.

Figure 6. "Standard" Petri net in ProM.

Figure 7. Petri net like representation produced by the data aware heuristic miner in ProM.

Inductive Visual Miner (IvM) Model

The inductive visual miner is a process mining discovery algorithm that comes with its own visualization. The model visualization follows the principles of process trees. According to the author, "IvM shows models in an intuitive formalism that closely resembles Petri nets, process trees, and BPMN models" [3].

Figure 8. IvM Model in ProM.

Causal Net

The Causal net, also called C-net is a “graph where nodes represent activities and arcs represent causal dependencies” [4]. Compared to Petri nets, in Causal nets, no places are displayed and the routing logic is only represented by the direct bindings of nodes.

Figure 9. Causal Net in ProM. Analysts can modify multiple parameters to mine a model that represents the event log well.

Social Network

The Social Network highlights the interactions and relationships between individuals or roles involved in a process. It typically uses metrics like frequency of communication or task handovers to reveal collaboration patterns, responsibility distribution, or potential bottlenecks in team dynamics.

Figure 10. Social Network in ProM. In our study, analyst used it to assess the relationship of activities instead of resources.

Business Process Model and Notation (BPMN)

BPMN is a graphical language for process management and provides symbols that allow to record, model, document, design, execute, measure, monitor, and control business processes.

Figure 11. BPMN Interface in Celonis. Users can generate a BPMN model by selecting variants of their choice or develop their own model from scratch.

Trace Sequence

Trace sequence visualizations display the events and attributes of one case (trace) in the log. They allow to assess the sequence of activities for the case, as well as attributes (e.g., timestamps) related to them.

Figure 12. Trace Sequence in ProM.

Figure 13. Trace Sequence in Disco.

Variants Sequence

Provides a visual overview of all variants in the log by displaying each group of traces that has the same control-flow order of activities. For easier recognition, activities are colored. When a variant is selected, all single traces are shown on the right and attribute values can be checked. Also, some metrics for each variant, as well as for each trace are shown.

Figure 14. Variants Sequence in ProM.

Dotted Chart

The dotted chart visualizes the raw data from the event log, displaying each event (row) in the data as one dot in a chart. Options allow to flexibly set the x- and y-axis and to specify the meaning of colors.

Figure 15. Dotted Chart in ProM

Line Graph

Figure 16. Line Graphs in Celonis and Disco.

Bar Chart

Figure 17. Bar Chart In Disco

Figure 18. Bar Chart in Celonis

Scatterplot

Figure 19. Classical Scatterplot in Celonis.

Focus Perspective – Coding Scheme

Below, we describe the different focus types to which analysts directed their attention while working with visualizations. For each focus type, we provide a description and report the total duration for which it was coded across all recordings (independent of overlaps with the visualization perspective).

During coding, we allowed focus codes to overlap. This means that within a single video segment, multiple focus types could be assigned. Codes might overlap when analysts attended simultaneously to several areas, e.g., process flow and process performance, or when analysts rapidly shifted their attention between different aspects of the process.

Focus	Description	min
Activities	Focus on specific activities (events) performed during the process to understand their role or identify them within a process model	209.5
Attributes	Further data attributes, such as payment amount, additional fine expenses, or car type.	111.8
Cases	Individual cases or process instances are typically assessed to understand complexity or gain an overview of a single case without a more specific focus on its flow or attributes.	27.8
Decision Points	Points in the process where branching occurs. Tools might provide decision rules for decision points.	12.9
Deviations	Discrepancies between the observed process and an expected or predefined process model.	9.4
Flow	Structure of the process, including frequent and less frequent paths or transitions between activities.	265.4
Performance	Time-related aspects of the process, such as the cycle time, throughput, or the distribution of events over time.	102.7
Statistic	Quantitative measures that summarize, describe, or evaluate characteristics of the event log, derived metrics, or process models. This includes basic counts (e.g., number of events or cases), analyst-defined metrics (e.g., payment rate), and algorithm-generated indicators (e.g., model fitness or confidence measures), computed for either the complete or a filtered event log.	230.9
Variants	Groups of control-flow paths of the process.	107.3

Task Perspective – Coding Scheme

Below, we describe the different analytical tasks that analysts pursued during their analysis in order to capture the underlying purpose of their activities. For the identification and definition of these tasks, we drew inspiration from the analysis processes proposed by Crisan et al. [8] and adapted them to the context of process mining. Based on this foundation, we defined generic analytical task categories, such as exploration and experimentation, tailored to process mining analysis.

Intent	Description	Example	min
Defining Need	Understanding the objectives and goals of the analysis.	p8: "Ok, so the question is the three most prevalent circumstances in which the fines and related expenses are not paid or paid not in full. All right. And for each circumstance, if possible from the information at your disposal, can you provide at least one reason that explains why the fines are not paid in full? Very nice."	66.8
Profiling	Assessing the event log to understand its structure, characteristics, and distribution of timestamps, events, and control-flow patterns.	p22: "OK, so what I first would do if I would start from the beginning, I would look at my event logs and all the other guidelines that I have with the data model in this part. So far, it seems to me at the beginning, quite, um, complicated. I would go back in this case to, um, to Celonis the environment, just look if the process has already been uploaded. So, I can see so I can get a high-level understanding of it."	256
Data Wrangling	Involves cleaning, transforming, or organizing data to ensure it is suitable for analysis.	p9: "The main problem for me currently is I want to see the ratio of my bad cases, let's say in any pie chart or any ratio, like it's partially are not paid in 10 percent and then it's partially not paid in 50 percent to go into a root cause analysis. I want to have one KPI where I can differentiate bad and good cases. "	112
Experimentation	Involves assessing or validating a hypothesis derived either from prior analysis insights or external knowledge.	p18: "My hypothesis is that between Create Fine and Send Fine, let's move to Disco to check that between Create Fine and Send Fine there is, um there might be some delay. So how can I do that?"	63.4
Exploration	Involves investigating the event log or process model without a predefined hypothesis. May include examining different process paths, variants, or attributes to find relevant insights related to the task without a predefined focused on any particular aspects.	p3: "So, let me take a little bit uh browse a little bit more. If I can spot something else. I'm not going to be able to find the three most prevalent reasons. But at least I feel that find one."	351
Descriptive Modeling	While still exploratory, descriptive modeling begins with the intent to describe specific features, metrics, attribute distributions, or control-flow aspects of the event log.	p16: "Then we're interested in the cases in which there was no payments, not in full. So we'll have a look at the paths that are also here, because that might give us an idea of the frequency of cases where there was no payments before the process closes. I can see here already that ..."	195
Diagnostic Modeling	Aims to uncover the underlying reasons for observed process behaviors, attribute values, or metrics.	p17: [Attempts to look into root causes for the situation he identified]: "There is a high number here. This one, I could do it in a different way, but there is also a high number. And this one is small, small, relatively small and high, so what I'm going to do is I'm going to filter that one and I'm going to try to understand what's going on in this case? Ok, that is 40% of the cases. Well. Let's see. I	115

		will try to be a bit more selective. Ok, though, it seems that it was credit recollection, that is a complicated one."	
Verification	Reflecting or actually checking the accuracy, validity, and completeness of the analysis results or the process to get there	p14: "Ok, so actually then we'll go back to process overview or to the Process Explorer, Variant Explorer doesn't end with payment, remove this condition. Ok, so it still looks quite similar. Maybe, but it seems like there was definitely a flaw in my logic. "	14.2
Interpretation	Making sense of the analysis results, understanding them in the context of the problem domain, or translating them into actionable insights or recommendations.	p11: "Already by looking here at the flow we can see those coming from another process step then payment and ending just there is a candidate for the root causes. But still keeping in mind that we need to do some filtering because it could be that the appeal court has not decided anything yet. So we are waiting for that. So more process steps or directions will occur or it could also be that we are going to pay, but we are not overdue yet. So, there is no reason for saying that, that the payment outstanding is a violation."	17.6

Event Sequences

Overview of the Visualization and Task Event Sequences per participant.

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